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Legal Consolidation of the Principles of Local Self-Government in Conditions of Sustainable Development

У статті визначено сутність та особливості правового закріплення принципів діяльності місцевого самоврядування в умовах сталого розвитку.

Зазначено, що забезпечення особистої безпеки громадян, захист прав і свобод, законних інтересів, запобігання правопорушенням та їх припинення, охорона і забезпечення громадського порядку, виявлення і розкриття злочинів, розшук осіб, які їх вчинили, забезпечення дорожнього руху, захист власності від протиправних посягань та інші завдання адміністративної діяльності органів внутрішніх справ можуть бути досягнуті тільки на основі дотримання її принципів.

Дослідження нормативного забезпечення діяльності місцевого самоврядування в умовах сталого розвитку та правового закріплення принципів діяльності місцевого самоврядування в умовах сталого розвитку, має науково-практичне значення, оскільки на теперішній час відсутні комплексні дослідження цієї проблеми.

Наголошено, що правове регулювання принципів діяльності місцевого самоврядування в умовах сталого розвитку забезпечується значною кількістю нормативно-правових актів, які відрізняються один від одного за назвою, порядком прийняття, юридичною силою тощо.

Підкреслено, що систему нормативно-правових актів, які регулюють принципи діяльності місцевого самоврядування в умовах сталого розвитку, можна поділити на чотири групи: Конституція України, Міжнародно-правові акти. Закони України. Нормативні акти Місцевого самоврядування.

Ключові слова: *правове закріплення, діяльність, особливість, закон, нормативно-правові акти, місцеве самоврядування, сталий розвиток, Україна.*

The article defines the essence and peculiarities of legal consolidation of the principles of local self-government in the conditions of sustainable development.

It is noted that ensuring personal safety of citizens, protection of rights and freedoms, legitimate interests, prevention of offenses and their termination, protection and maintenance of public order, detection and disclosure of crimes, search for persons who committed them, ensuring road traffic, protection of property from illegal encroachments and other tasks of the administrative activity of internal affairs bodies can be achieved only on the basis of compliance with its principles.

The study of regulatory support of local self-government activities in conditions of sustainable development and legal consolidation of the principles of local self-government activities in conditions of sustainable development, has scientific and practical importance, since there are currently no comprehensive studies of this problem.

It is emphasized that the legal regulation of the principles of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development is ensured by a significant number of normative legal acts, which differ from each other in terms of name, order of adoption, legal force, etc.

It is emphasized that the system of normative legal acts that regulate the principles of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development can be divided into four groups: the Constitution of Ukraine, international legal acts. Laws of Ukraine. Normative acts of Local Self-Government.

Keywords: *legal consolidation, activity, feature, law, normative legal acts, local self-government, sustainable development, Ukraine.*

Formulation of the problem. Ensuring personal safety of citizens, protection of rights and freedoms, legitimate interests, prevention of offenses and their termination, protection and maintenance of public order, detection and disclosure of crimes, search for persons who committed them, ensuring road traffic, protection of property from illegal encroachments and other tasks of administrative activities of internal affairs bodies can be achieved only on the basis of compliance with its principles.

In our opinion, the study of the regulatory support of local self-government activities in the conditions of sustainable development and the legal consolidation of the principles of local self-government activities in the conditions of sustainable development has scientific and practical importance, since there are currently no comprehensive studies of this problem.

Conducting research on this topic will allow to identify gaps in the current legislation and to formulate certain proposals for its improvement.

In our opinion, the improvement of the legal consolidation of principles, which will fully comply with international norms and standards, will help to increase the efficiency and coherence of the work of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development, and as a result, the trust and change of the population's attitude towards them.

In order to reflect our own visions regarding the improvement of the legal consolidation of the principles of the administrative activity of local self-government in the conditions of sustainable development, we consider it necessary to consider the existing normative legal acts, in which the principles of the activity of local self-government in the conditions of sustainable development are fixed to one degree or another.

Analysis of recent research and publications. General issues of local self-government activity were the subject of scientific research by S. M. Alforyov, M. I. Anufriev, O. M. Bandurka, V. M. Beschastny, V. T. Bilous, I. P. Holosnichenko, O. P. Hetmanets, S. M. Husarova, S. F. Denisyuk, I. V. Zozuli, R. A. Kalyuzhny, O. M. Klyuev, V. V. Kovalenko, A. T. Komzyuk, Y. F. Kravchenko, A. M. Kulisha, K. B. Levchenko, M. V. Loshytskyi, V. V. Malikova, N. P. Matyukhina, O. I. Mykolenko, R. V. Myronyuk, O. I. Nikitenko, O. V

, H. P. Yarmaki and other scientists. However, despite a sufficiently large number of scientific works on various areas of local self-government activity, the issue of legal consolidation of the principles of local self-government activity in conditions of sustainable development, highlighted fragmentarily, within the broader legal issues, correspondingly, the problems of the theoretical, organizational and legal nature of their activity remained unresolved, which emphasizes the expediency of scientific research on the researched issues.

Thus, the need to improve and systematically renew the activities of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development, the forms and methods of their management activities, the imperfection of legal regulation in this area and the lack of complex scientific research on this issue determine the relevance and indicate the need for a comprehensive study of the legal consolidation of the principles of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development.

The purpose of this article is to determine the essence and peculiarities of the legal consolidation of the principles of local self-government in the conditions of sustainable development.

Presenting main material. Legal regulation of the principles of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development is provided by a significant number of normative legal acts, which differ from each other in terms of name, order of adoption, legal force, etc.

The system of normative legal acts that regulate the principles of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development can be divided into four groups:

1. The Constitution of Ukraine,
2. International legal acts.
3. Laws of Ukraine.
4. Normative acts of Local Self-Government

[1, p. 122].

Let's focus on the two main ones:

1. Constitution of Ukraine. Has the highest legal force. Laws and other normative legal acts are adopted on the basis of the Constitution of Ukraine and must comply with it [2].

The Constitution of Ukraine does not establish the principles of administrative activity of local self-government in the conditions of sustainable development directly, but stipulates the general principles of organizing the activities of state bodies. Since local self-government is a component of the executive power, the principles enshrined in the Constitution are fundamental for the operation of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development. Example:

- the principle of the rule of law (Article 8);
- the principle of equality before the law (Article 24);
- the principle of impartial treatment of people (Article 34);
- the principle of affirming and ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens (Article 3);
- the principle of respect for dignity (Article 28);
- the principle of social justice (Article 1).

Therefore, these basic principles should also be defined in other normative legal acts that regulate the activities of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development.

2. Laws of Ukraine.

The most important role in the system of legislative acts that regulate the administrative activity of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development is played by the Law of Ukraine "On Local Self-Government in Ukraine". The Law defines and enshrines the concept of local self-government, main tasks, organizational and legal basis of local self-government, principles of activity, material and financial basis of local self-government. Thus, according to Article 4 of the Law of Ukraine "On Local Self-Government in Ukraine", the activities of the militia are based on the principles of local self-government in Ukraine based on the principles of: people's rule; legality; publicity; collegiality; combination of local and state interests; electability; legal, organizational and material and financial independence within the limits of the powers defined by this and other laws; accountability and responsibility to territorial communities of their bodies and officials; state support and guarantee of local self-government; judicial protection of the rights of local self-government. [3].

In our opinion, the system of principles in the Law of Ukraine "On Principles of Prevention and Counteraction of Corruption" [4] has been very successfully defined.

In accordance with Article 3 of this Law, the activity of preventing and combating corruption is based on the principles of:

- rule of law;
- legality;
- comprehensive implementation of legal, political, socio-economic, informational and other measures;
- priority of preventive measures;
- the inevitability of responsibility for committing corruption offenses;
- openness and transparency of activities of state authorities and local self-government bodies;
- public participation in measures to prevent and counter corruption, state protection of persons who provide assistance in the implementation of such measures.

In our opinion, within the scope of the Law, such a list of principles is exhaustive, because it reflects the main principles of state institutions authorized to prevent and counter such a socially dangerous phenomenon as corruption.

The Law of Ukraine "On service in local self-government bodies" defines a system of principles: service in local self-government bodies is carried out in compliance with the following principles [5]:

1) the rule of law - ensuring the priority of the rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen in accordance with the Constitution of Ukraine, which determine the content and direction of activities during the implementation of the functions and powers of local self-government;

2) legality - the obligation to act only on the basis, within the limits of authority and in the manner provided by the Constitution and laws of Ukraine;

3) patriotism - devotion and faithful service to the Ukrainian people;

4) service to territorial communities - the focus of activity on the implementation and protection of the right of territorial communities to local self-government, ensuring their legitimate interests, defined by the Constitution and laws of Ukraine;

5) a combination of local and state interests - the obligation to take into account the principles of state policy in the relevant field (sphere) during the exercise of powers;

6) integrity - the orientation of actions to the protection of public interests and the refusal of the predominance of private interest during the exercise of powers;

7) efficiency - rational and effective use of resources for the implementation of functions and powers of local self-government and separate powers of executive bodies granted by law;

8) equal access to service in local self-government bodies - the prohibition of all forms and manifestations of discrimination, the absence of unjustified restrictions or the granting of unjustified advantages to certain categories of citizens during the entry into service in local self-government bodies and its completion;

9) professionalism - competent, objective and impartial performance of official duties, constant improvement of the level of professional competence;

10) political impartiality - preventing the influence of political views on actions and decisions, as well as refraining from demonstrating one's attitude to political parties, demonstrating one's own political views during the performance of official duties;

11) transparency - informing about the activities of local self-government officials, except for the cases specified by the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, guaranteeing free access to information about the activities of local self-government officials in the scope and order determined by law;

12) openness - involvement of the public, including by holding public consultations, in the discussion of issues related to the development, adoption and implementation of acts of local self-government bodies, implementation of other powers of local self-government bodies;

13) stability - the appointment of local self-government employees for an indefinite period, except for the cases provided for by law, the independence of the personnel of local self-government employees from the change of service managers;

14) independence of service management in local self-government bodies - non-interference of state authorities or their officials in the exercise by local self-government bodies and their officials of their authority to manage services in local self-government bodies;

15) responsibility - personal legal responsibility for improper performance and failure to perform official duties [5, 6, p. 145].

Conclusions. Summing up, it should be noted that during the analysis of the legal

consolidation of the principles of the administrative activity of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development, we came to the conclusion that the system of legal acts regulating the principles of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development can be divided into four groups:

1. The Constitution of Ukraine, which does not directly establish the principles of the administrative activity of the internal affairs bodies of Ukraine, but conditions the general principles of the organization of the activities of state bodies. Since the internal affairs bodies are part of the executive authorities, the principles enshrined in the Constitution are fundamental for the administrative activity of the internal affairs bodies of Ukraine and should be reflected in other legal acts regulating the activities of the internal affairs bodies.

2. International legal acts.

3. Laws of Ukraine.

4. Normative acts of Local Self-Government.

Therefore, we believe that in each normative legal act, which regulates the activities of local self-government in the conditions of sustainable development, the principles on the basis of which the activities of this or that subdivision will be carried out must be established.

Unfortunately, some of them do not include in their structure such a category as a principle, which, in our opinion, is unacceptable, because any activity, including the administrative activity of local self-government in conditions of sustainable development, must be guided by certain principles, which must be fixed at the legislative level.

The principles of such activity should be enshrined in the general provisions of normative legal acts, since the principles are the basis, foundation, and beginning. The principles should be general, fundamental, because they form organizational principles that determine the essence, characteristics and general directions of local self-government activities in conditions of sustainable development.

Prospective further scientific research should determine the essence and peculiarities of the legal consolidation of the principles of local self-government in the conditions of sustainable development in the member states of the European Union.

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